

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

S P U B L I S H I N G

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 2 | APRIL - JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“BREAKING THE SILENCE: ENDING ABUSE AGAINST WOMEN”

Pain and beauty reside in the same being.
Her smile never defines her veins, merely acts as a mask.
Sculpted to not love the blue skies whispers a tragedy of a broken word scream.
Somewhere in a cabin, chains and silence restrain her voice;

Dread her heart, walking step by step on a shoelace dipped in rager-red blood.
Suffering from depression, the weight of “I am sorry” is muted to a whisper.
My point where mirrors rage came long before putting glass into shards, aimlessly rushing like tide, breezy
essence and crashing into pillars is what surviving as feels.

She misplaced truth with obeying commands deemed by codeine aching veins.
Motor skills and emotions fight in a single body containing a nuclear war fueled with despair Rest shakes
when choosing arms relatable to cheeky pixie dust not blushing.
She carries more weight than the scars of my self-inflicted wounds.

Cowering from others' need not fear raised burnt pillows of self-assertiveness.
And guarded when sensing unearned tender strokes of nobleness
Her form stunning vessel waiting to be loved fills.
Her soul survives as remains of pain.